

Optimal Design of Seamless C/SiC Combustor with Multi-Cooling Channels for Rocket Engines Based on a Data-Driven Model

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Contents

I. Introduction

II. Methodology

III. Results and Discussions

Contents

I. Introduction

II. Methodology

III. Results and Discussions

The rise of hypersonic technology: a global strategic priority

US hypersonic programmes to receive almost **\$7 billion** in 2025

2nd April 2024 - 10:23 GMT | by Flavia Camargos Pereira in Kansas City

Rocket Lab Onramped To Multi-**Billion Dollar** U.S. and U.K. Defense Contracts To Expand Hypersonic Technology Development with HASTE

Provided by Business Wire • Apr 15, 2025 6:00am

Europe Hypersonic Missiles Market to Surpass **USD 2 Billion** by 2032 with Strong Growth

Report Ocean Mar. 11, 2025 12:01

[Hypersonic weapons and alternatives]

(Source: Congressional Budget Office, <https://www.cbo.gov/publication/58924>)

Combustor: key element in hypersonic engines

[Hypersonic vehicle and combustor schematic]

High Performance Computing in Science and Engineering 2011, 429–441

Materials and cooling strategies for extreme conditions

■ Ceramic matrix composites (CMCs)

Trans Indian Inst Met (2019) 72(8):2043–2059

[Specific fast-rupture strength of different materials]

■ Regenerative cooling

Aerospace 2023, 10(1), 65

In cooling channel: high P

[Schematic of regenerative cooling]

PTAH-SOCAR: leading technique, but

Winding

Pinning

Winding

[PTAH-SOCAR process]

Progress in Propulsion Physics 1 (2009) 627-644

- ✓ Complex-shaped combustor composites are manufactured through a combined winding and pinning process.
- ✓ However, **mechanical joints interrupt the continuity of cooling channels**, causing stress concentration and reducing structural strength. → need of seamless structures

Advanced weaving technology for seamless structures

Double-tubular composites

Polymer Composites. 2024;45:8282–8295

[Double-tubular composites with woven architecture]

Box-shaped composites

Heliyon 10 (2024) e2412

[Box-shaped composites with woven architecture]

Need of structural optimization

Research goal

Goal: fabrication of seamless combustors with multi-cooling channels

1. Optimization of cooling channels considering

(1) Burst resistance, (2) Weight, (3) Pressure drop of coolant, (4) Cooling performance

2. Development of fabrication method for seamless combustors with cooling channels

Research outline

1. Optimization of cooling channels considering

(1) Burst resistance, (2) Weight, (3) Pressure drop of coolant, (4) Cooling performance

n_{AC}
 n_{TC}
 L_a
 L_t
 t_i
 t_o
 h

- (1) Burst resistance (f_1)
: AI model
- (2) Weight (f_2)
: # of used connectors
- (3) Pressure drop (f_3)
: analogy model
- (4) Cooling (f_4)
: contact area of coolant

Contents

I. Introduction

II. Methodology

III. Results and Discussions

Numerical models for burst simulation

[Full model and half model of the combustors]

[Numerical model]

- ✓ To reduce the computing time for simulation of bursting, a cyclic half-section (i.e., half model) of the combustor was selected for analysis.
- ✓ Boundary conditions:
z-symmetry and **radial/axial free + axial load**
- ✓ Mesh and element:
0.3 mesh size / Hex-dominated (structured) / C3D8R

Simulation conditions

■ Loading conditions

■ Materials: 2D C/SiC composites

[High thermal performance of C/SiC composites]

E_1	E_2	E_3	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}	G_{12}	G_{13}	G_{23}
	[MPa]			-			[MPa]	
60100	60100	48400	0.1	0.05	0.05	25000	20000	20000
X_T	Y_T	Z_T	X_C	Y_C	Z_C	S_{12}	S_{13}	S_{23}
				[MPa]				
98.9	98.9	11.4	265	265	62	57.5	35.3	35.3

[Material properties of 2D C/SiC composites]

[Cross-sectional view of internal pressure and axial force]

Parameters for burst resistance

- ✓ The most commonly used criteria, Tsai-Wu (F_{TW}),

is chosen as failure factor: *Composite Structures 337 (2024) 118099*

$$F_1\sigma_1 + F_2\sigma_2 + F_3\sigma_3 + F_4\sigma_4 + F_5\sigma_5 + F_6\sigma_6 + F_{11}\sigma_1^2 + F_{22}\sigma_2^2 + F_{33}\sigma_3^2 + F_{44}\sigma_4^2 + F_{55}\sigma_5^2 + F_{66}\sigma_6^2 + 2F_{12}\sigma_1\sigma_2 + 2F_{13}\sigma_1\sigma_3 + 2F_{23}\sigma_2\sigma_3 < 1.0$$

where $F_i = \frac{1}{\sigma_{it}} - \frac{1}{\sigma_{ic}}$ for $i = 1,2,3, F_4 = F_5 = F_6 = 0$,

$$F_{ii} = \frac{1}{\sigma_{it}\sigma_{ic}} \text{ for } i = 1,2,3,$$

$$F_{jj} = \frac{1}{\tau_{jk}^2} \text{ for shear } (j = 4,5,6, jk = 12,23,31)$$

$$F_{ij} = -\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{F_{ii}F_{jj}} \text{ for } ij = 12, 23, 31$$

Composites Part C:Open Access 4 (2021) 100122

- ✓ 3 individual, maximum index values are extracted by the part:

- I. F_{TW}^{InL} in inner layer
- II. F_{TW}^{OutL} in outer layer
- III. F_{TW}^{Con} in connector

Design parameters ($n_{AC}, n_{TC}, L_a, L_t, t_i, t_o, h$)

Pressure drop in cooling channels

[Repeating structure of cooling channels]

- ✓ A representative repeating unit is defined.
- ✓ It is assumed that the pressure drop behavior within the repeating unit occurs in 5 steps.

Analogy model for pressure drop

[Hagen-Poiseuille equation]

Assumptions

- ✓ Incompressible fluid
- ✓ Laminar flow
- ✓ Steady state

Boundary conditions

(1) by 4 walls

$$u\left(\pm \frac{b}{2}, y\right) = 0$$

$$u\left(x, \pm \frac{c}{2}\right) = 0$$

(2) by 2 walls

$$u(\pm\infty, y) = 0$$

$$u\left(x, \pm \frac{c}{2}\right) = 0$$

Friction loss by 4 walls

$$\Delta P_1 = \frac{12\mu QL}{bc^3} \left\{ 1 - \frac{c}{b} \frac{192}{\pi^5} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \tanh\left(\frac{c(2n-1)\pi}{b}\right) \frac{1}{(2n-1)^5} \right\}^{-1}$$

Friction loss by 2 walls

$$\Delta P_2 = \frac{12\mu QL}{bc^3}$$

Form loss

$$\Delta P_3 = K \frac{\rho u_m^2}{2}$$

$$\therefore \Delta P_{out} = 2 \cdot \Delta P_1 + \Delta P_2 + \Delta P_3 + \Delta P_4$$

✓ Assuming steady-state laminar coolant flow: pressure drop in a rectangular channel is calculated. → establishment of **pressure drop analogy model** for objective function

b: width (mm)
c: height (mm)
Q: volumetric flow rate (m³/s)
μ: dynamic viscosity (Pa · s)
L: length (mm)
ρ: density (kg/m³)
u_m: mean flow rate (m²/s)
K: form loss coefficient

Contents

I. Introduction

II. Methodology

III. Results and Discussions

Burst simulation results: $F_{TW}(>1)$ distribution

[Axial cross-sectional view of half models]

- (a) combustor 1: (69, 28, 1, 1, 3, 3, 3)
- (b) combustor 2: (57, 30, 2, 3, 2, 3, 1)
- (c) combustor 3: (44, 36, 1, 1, 1, 2, 2)

$(n_{AC}, n_{TC}, L_a, L_t, t_i, t_o, h)$

 : safe zone

Training and performance of AI models

[Predicted vs actual values]
(R^2 close to 1 implies strong predictive performance on the test set.)

[Results of hyper parameter tuning]

✓ **800 datasets** were obtained.

→ Hyperparameter tuning for building a high-performance AI model architecture

✓ Adam optimizer, ReLU activation function, max 100-iteration learning condition

Validation of pressure drop analogy model

[Geometric conditions of the repeating units for comparison simulations]

[Example of pressure drop simulation]

- ✓ The validity of the analogy model was demonstrated by comparing its results with those obtained from COMSOL.
- : water is used as coolant

	(%)	Tangential Length (mm)		
		0	10	30
Inlet Width (mm)	1	0.9	2.6	3.8
	5	1.4	3.05	3.3
	10	1.8	3.0	3.0

[Error rate of pressure drop]

Definition of optimization problem

- Burst resistance $f_1 = \frac{1}{3} (F_{TW}^{InL} + F_{TW}^{OutL} + F_{TW}^{Con})$

- Weight

$$f_2 = \frac{W_{connector}}{W_{connector}^{Max}}$$

- Pressure loss

$$f_3 = \frac{\Delta P_{out}}{\Delta P_{Max}}$$

- Cooling

$$f_4 = 1 - \frac{ConArea}{ConArea_{Max}}$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{minimize} \quad f_1 \\ \quad \quad \quad f_2 + f_3 + f_4 \\ \text{where, } X = [n_{AC}, n_{TC}, L_a, L_t, t_i, t_o, h] \end{array} \right.$$

✓ Definition of 4 objective functions

f_1 : AI model, f_3 : analogy model

f_2 : total weight of connectors, f_4 : contact area

✓ Definition of a two-objective optimization problem

Exploration for $W_{connector}^{Max}$, ΔP_{Max} , $ConArea_{Max}$

*Boundary conditions

$$\begin{aligned} 10 &\leq n_{AC} \leq 70 & 1 &\leq L_t \leq 3 \\ 20 &\leq n_{TC} \leq 36 & 1 &\leq t_i \leq 3 \\ 1 &\leq L_a \leq 5 & 1 &\leq t_o \leq 3 \\ & & 1 &\leq h \leq 3 \end{aligned}$$

- ✓ To normalize the performance objective functions (f_2, f_3, f_4), reference values were investigated.
- ✓ Tsai-Wu-based f_1 was normalized between 0 and 1.

Region where the channel width < 4 mm

(70, 20, 5, 3, 3, 3, 3)

(70, 22, 4, 3, 1, 1, 1)

[Results of exploration]

(70, 36, 1, 3, 3, 1, 3)

Optimization algorithm for multi-objective problem

✓ Application of **Non-Dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II)** via Python programming

***NSGA-II**: a genetic algorithm-based multi-objective optimization method for deriving a single Pareto front

*Pareto front: group of optimized solutions

✓ Conditions for optimization process: **population size = 500, the number of generation = 50**

Verma, Shanu, Millie Pant, and Vaclav Snasel. *IEEE access* 9 (2021): 57757-57791.

Optimization results

[Initial population and optimal solutions with corresponding simulation results]

Optimized combustor designs within the design space

[Convergence of $f_2 + f_3 + f_4$ during optimization]

Best $f_2 + f_3 + f_4$ value in given datasets: **0.525**

	F_{TW}^{InL}	F_{TW}^{OutL}	F_{TW}^{Con}	w	ΔP	S
		-		[Kg]	[Pa]	[m ²]
Conv.	6.37	6.50	2.69	87.5	0.024	0.31
$(n_{AC}, n_{TC}, L_a, L_t, t_i, t_o, h) = (64, 36, 1, 2, 1, 3, 3)$						

Optimization

Optimal $f_2 + f_3 + f_4$ value in given design space: **0.490**

	F_{TW}^{InL}	F_{TW}^{OutL}	F_{TW}^{Con}	w	ΔP	S
		-		[Kg]	[Pa]	[m ²]
Opt.	4.65	6.60	4.70	95.2	0.026	0.33
$(n_{AC}, n_{TC}, L_a, L_t, t_i, t_o, h) = (70, 36, 1, 2, 3, 1, 3)$						
Sim.	6.81	7.16	3.47		-	

Conclusions

- I. Four quantitative metrics and objective functions were established.
- II. **Burst performance was predicted using AI models** and applied to structural optimization.
- III. Further studies will explore **design constraints and target-based optimization**.
- IV. The final composite combustor will be **seamlessly fabricated** and tested for validation.

Thank you / Q&A

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Appendix. Full model vs Half model

Appendix. Material orientation (1)

Appendix. Material orientation (2)

Appendix. Friction loss model

- ✓ Incompressible fluid
- ✓ Laminar flow
- ✓ Steady state

Friction loss by 4 walls

$$(1) \quad u\left(\pm \frac{b}{2}, y\right) = 0$$

$$u\left(x, \pm \frac{c}{2}\right) = 0$$

$$Q = \frac{Kbc^3}{12\mu} \left\{ 1 - \frac{c}{b} \frac{192}{\pi^5} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \tanh\left(\frac{c(2n-1)\pi}{b(2n-1)^5}\right) \right\}$$

Friction loss by 2 walls

$$(2) \quad u(\pm\infty, y) = 0$$

$$u\left(x, \pm \frac{c}{2}\right) = 0$$

$$u = \frac{K}{2\mu} \left[\frac{1}{4} c^2 - y^2 \right]$$

$$Q = \frac{Kbc^3}{12\mu}$$

K: the pressure gradient (ΔP)
b: width (mm)
c: height (mm)
Q: volumetric flow rate (m^3/s)
μ: dynamic viscosity ($Pa \cdot s$)
L: length (mm)

Appendix. Form loss model

그림. form loss coefficient (Expansion)

그림. form loss coefficient (Contraction)

Sharp-Edged $K_L=1.0$

$$\Delta p = K \frac{\rho u_m^2}{2}$$

ρ : density (kg/m^3)

u_m : mean flow rate (m^2/s)

K : form loss coefficient

$$K_E = (1 - \sigma)^2$$

$$K_C = 0.5(1 - \sigma)^2$$

σ : area ratio

Sharp-Edged $K_L=0.5$

<https://sbainvent.com/fluid-mechanics/minor-head-loss/>

Appendix. CFD simulation conditions

Pipe		Rectangular (3D)	
Type		Height	Length
[-]		[h, m]	[L, m]
smooth		0.001	0.05

Fluid		water	
Inlet Pressure	Outlet Velocity	Density	Dynamic viscosity
[Pa]	[m/s]	[ρ , kg/m ³]	[μ , Pa·s]
1	0.0001	1000	0.001

Appendix. Equation for f_2, f_4

\therefore for f_2 , Weight
 $= \text{density of CMC} * n_{AC}(n_{TC} - 1) * abc$

\therefore for f_4 , Total Contact Area (ConArea)
 $= \text{Area of Inner layer} + \text{Area of Outer Area}$
 $+ n_{AC}(n_{TC} - 1)(2(ac + bc) - 2ab)$